

New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Burning Number From Graph Searching

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1 SYNOPSIS

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyper_{Burning Number}). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V_s' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then V_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyper_{Burning Number} if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyper_{Burning Number} criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned} & |(\sum_{V_i \in V_s'} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s'} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s'} F(V_i))| \\ &= \min_{V_s'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |\{(\sum_{V_i \in V_s''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} F(V_i)) | \\ & \quad V_j \in V_s'', \\ & \quad \text{then } N_s^*(V_i) \in V_s'', \\ & \quad \text{until } V_{NSHG} \setminus_s V_s'' = \emptyset, \}|. \end{aligned}$$

In this scientific research, new configurations are introduced for the new SuperHyperNotions, namely a Burning Number and a Neutrosophic Burning Number. Two different SuperHyperDefinitions were started for them, but research has progressed and SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform, and SuperHyperClass are well-defined and well-reviewed based on them. Literature review is implemented throughout this research. To shine the light and importance of this research, a comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions and basic SuperHyperNumbers is presented. Definitions are followed by examples and examples, so clarifications are guided by various tools. Applications are designed to understand the theoretical aspect of this ongoing research. “Cancer diagnosis” are the things that are being researched to explore the challenges that make sense in ongoing research and future research. It is a special case. Cells are viewed in the intended manner. There are different types of them. Some are individual and some are well modeled by groups of cells. All these types are officially called “SuperHyperVertex”, but the relationships between them all are officially called “SuperHyperEdge”. “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” frameworks are selected and selected for research on “Cancer Diagnosis”. Thus, these complex and dense super-hypermodels open avenues for research on theoretical aspects and “cancer diagnosis”. Ways to pursue this scientific research have been considered. It has also been formally collected in the form of several questions and problems. It is useful to define a “neutrosophic” version of Burning Number. Since there are more ways to get type results a Burning Number becomes more understandable. In order to master the Neutrosophic Burning Number, there is a need to “re-define” the concept of “Burning Number mastery”. SuperHyperVertices and

SuperHyperEdges are assigned by alphabetical labels. In this method, the position of tags is used to assign values. Suppose a Burning Number. If the specified table contains “values of vertices, supervertices, edges, hyperedges, and hyperedges belonging to Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” with key points, it is redefined. ”values of vertices & number of positions in alphabet”, ”Values of SuperVertices&maximum values of its vertices”, ”values of edges&maximum values of its vertices”, ”super edge values&max values of its vertices”, “super edge values” and maximum values of its endpoints”. To get examples and structural examples, I would like to introduce the next SuperHyperClass SuperHyperGraph based on Burning Number. This is the original. Having the foundation of the previous definition in the SuperHyperClass type would be disciplined. If there is a need to have all Burning Number until Burning Number, then it is officially called “Burning Number”, but otherwise, it is not Burning Number. There is some explanation for the original definition titled “Burning Number”. These two examples are further explored and distinguished because they are characterized in the SuperHyperClass disciplinary methods based on a dominant Burning Number. Because of having Burning Number, there is a need to “re-define” the concept of “neutrosophic Burning Number” and “neutrosophic Burning Number”. SuperHyperVertices and SuperHyperEdges are assigned by alphabetical labels. In this method, the position of tags is used to assign values. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” is redefined if the desired table exists. And if the desired table exists, a Burning Number is redefined to a “Neutrosophic Burning Number”. It is useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there are more ways to obtain Neutrosophic type results, a SuperHyper- Neutrosophic Burning Number becomes more understandable. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If the desired table exists, there are a number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. So are SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite and SuperHyperWheel. ”Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel”. A graph is SuperHyperUniform if it is a SuperHyperGraph and the number of SuperHyperEdges elements is the same. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are a number of SuperHyperClasses as follows. It is a SuperHyperPath if there is only one SuperVertex as an intersection between two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions. If only one SuperVertex is given as an intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, it is SuperHyperCycle. It is SuperHyperStar and only one SuperVertex as intersection among all SuperHyperEdges. It is SuperHyperBipartite, and only one SuperVertex is given as the intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, and these SuperVertices, which form two distinct sets, have no SuperHyperEdge in common. This is SuperHyperMultiPartite. Only one SuperVertex is given as an intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, and these SuperVertices, which form separate multisets, have no SuperHyperEdge in common. If only one SuperHyperEdge among the given two SuperHyperEdges is a SuperHyperWheel and a SuperVertex has a SuperHyperEdge with any regular SuperVertex. SuperHyperModel suggests specific designs and specific architectures. SuperHyperModel is officially called “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. In this SuperHyperModel, the “special” cells and the “special group” of cells are SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperVertices” and the common and desired properties between the “special” cells and the “special group” of cells. SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperEdges”. Sometimes, to have a more accurate SuperHyperModel, it is useful to have some degree of determinism, uncertainty, and neutrality, in this case the SuperHyperModel is called “Neutrosophic”. In future scientific research, the foundation will be based on “diagnosis of cancer” and the results and definitions will be introduced in redeemed methods. Cancer diagnosis in long-term practice. The specific region is assigned by the model

(called SuperHyperGraph) and the long cycle of movement of the cancer is determined by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of cancer is not easy to detect, because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of cancer on that area. This event leads us to choose another model [which is said to be the Neutrosophic superhypergraph] in order to have a proper understanding of what happened and was done. There are some specific models, which are well known and have names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The movements and effects of cancer in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized with a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find the longest Burning Number or the strongest Burning Number in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. Some general results are presented for the longest Burning Number called Burning Number and the strongest Burning Number called Neutrosophic Burning Number. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges, but it is not enough as having at least three SuperHyperEdges is necessary to form any style of cycle. There is no form of any cycle, but literally, it is the transformation of any cycle. It literally transforms and does not form. A basic introduction to the theory of Burning Number Neutrosophic, SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs is suggested.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyper_{Burning Number}, Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are ideas in the prominent frameworks of motivations. I try to bring motivations in narrative ways. Some Cells have faced attacks from the established situation with cancer attacks in this case, there is some analysis embedded in the case current situations where cells can be labeled as some groups and some groups or individuals are overlabeled, all from behaviors to overcome cancer attacks. In embedded situations, cell individuals and cell groups can be considered as “new groups”. So it encourages us to find suitable SuperHyperModels for more appropriate analysis about this dirty story. I found SuperHyperModels, officially called “SuperHyperGraphs” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. In this SuperHyperModel, cells and groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperVertices” and relationships between individual cells and groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperEdges”. So this is another motivation for us to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on “cancer diagnosis”. Sometimes, things get worse. The situation has passed certainty and precise style. So it is beyond them. There are three descriptions, i.e., degrees of determination, uncertainty, and neutrality, for any object based on ambiguous forms, i.e., incomplete data, imprecise data, and uncertain analysis. The second model can be considered in the previous SuperHyperModel. This is SuperHyperModel. This is SuperHyperGraph but officially called “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Cancer is a disease, but the model is supposed to understand what happens in this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and some parameters are used as consequences of the model. Cells are attacked by the disease, but the movement of cancer is in a specific area. Knowing the mind of cancer can help to find some cures for this disease. SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic Super-HyperGraph are super-hypermodels used in “cancer diagnosis” and both are the foundation of the background of this scientific research. Sometimes cancer has occurred in an area full of cells, cell groups, and embedded styles. In this section,

SuperHyperModel proposes based on the links of cancer movements in the form of unity styles with the formation of design and architecture officially called “Burning Number”, in the themes of specialized terms and common words. Particle for direct object. Applied concepts under the investigation of the motivation of this scientific research. The “SuperHyper” prefix refers to the theme of embedded styles for background discovery for SuperHyperNotions. Cancer diagnosis in long-term practice. The specific region is assigned by the model (called SuperHyperGraph) and the long cycle of movement of the cancer is determined by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of Cancer is not easy to identify because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of Cancer in that region. This event leads us to choose another model [said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph]. Easy understanding of what happened and what was done. There are some specific models that are well known and named and some general models. The movements and effects of cancer in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized by a neutrosophic superhyperpath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find Burning Number or Neutrosophic Burning Number for SuperHyperModels in it. Some general results are presented. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges, but it is not enough as having at least three SuperHyperEdges is necessary to form any style of cycle. There is no form of cycle, but it is literally a form of any cycle. It literally transforms and does not form.

Question 2.1. *How to define “SuperHyperNotions and to do research” to find the “Burning Number Rate” of any cell or groups of cells based on fixed cell or fixed group of cells broadly, “Burning Number Rate” based on fixed groups or fixed cells. Groups of groups of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for “diagnosing cancer” in terms of these chaotic and dense super-hypermodels in which embedded concepts are depicted?*

This motivation to find concepts to use in this dense model is called “SuperHyperGraphs”. So it motivates us to define different types of “Burning Number” and “neutrosophic Burning Number” over “superhypergraph” and “neutrosophic superhypergraph”. Then this scientific research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and find some connections among this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to obtain examples and examples to clarify the framework of this scientific research. The general results and some of the results about some of the connections are the ways that the key point of this scientific research, “diagnosis of cancer” is more understandable and clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. First, I will introduce the basic definitions to clarify the basics. In the “Introductions” subsection, basic definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are introduced and discussed in depth. Basic concepts are thoroughly explained and illustrated, and sometimes a literature review is used to make sense of what is to come in the coming sections. The main definitions and their explanations, along with some results on the new concepts, Burning Number and Neutrosophic Burning Number, are specified in the sections “Burning Number” and “Neutrosophic Burning Number”. In the concept of dealing with results and in Burning Number to create logic about the continuation of the scientific research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their consequences, the corresponding SuperHyperClasses are specified to summarize the work done in this section, as “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. Going back to the core concepts, clever steps towards common concepts to extend new concepts in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, in “Results

on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” sections. There is the initial scientific research on supergeneral relations and as the final and final part of the theoretical scientific research is available in the section “General results”. Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and are known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions, as in “General results” were extracted and discussed. “Burning Number”, “Neutrosophic Burning Number”, “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. There are curious questions about what has been done about SuperHyperNotions to make sense of the superiority of this scientific research and to discover the word “best” as a description and adjective of this scientific research as presented in the “Burning Number” section. The keyword of this scientific research was presented in the section “Applications in cancer diagnosis” with two cases and sub-sections “Case 1: Initial steps towards SuperHyperBipartite as SuperHyperModel” and “Case 2: Incremental steps towards SuperHyperMultiperdel as SuperHyper”. In the “open issues” section, there is a detailed examination and recognition of what was done in this scientific research and what happened in this scientific research in the form of “questions” and “issues” in order to understand this scientific research in an outstanding style, the advantages and limitations of this scientific research in addition to What has been done in this scientific research is stated in the “conclusion and final remarks” section.

3 Neutrosophic Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](Ref. [1],Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](Ref. [1],Definition 2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [1],Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [1],Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [1],Definition 2.7,p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths] (Ref. [1],Definition 5.3,p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)] (Ref. [1],Definition 5.4,p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to Ref. [1].

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [1],Definition 2.1,p.1).

Let X be a Eulerian-Path-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ define respectively the a **truth-membership function**, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a **falsity-membership function** of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$^{-}0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+.$$

The functions $T_A(x), I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]-0, 1^+[$.

Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [1],Definition 2.2,p.2).

Let X be a Eulerian-Path-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by

truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$T_A(X) = \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$F_A(X) = \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (**Ref.** [1], Definition 2.5,p.2).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'})) : T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$F'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}}$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$.

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V .

Figure 1. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

$T'_V(E_{i'})$, $T'_V(E_{i'})$, and $T'_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' 'th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Example 3.6. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic notion, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint.
- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic notion, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint.
- On the Figure (3), the SuperHyperNotion, namely, SuperHyperGirth, is up. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 .
- On the Figure (4), there's no empty SuperHyperEdge but E_3 are a loop SuperHyperEdge on $\{F\}$ and there are some SuperHyperEdges, namely, E_1 on $\{H, V_1, V_3\}$, alongside E_2 on $\{O, H, V_4, V_3\}$ and E_4, E_5 on $\{N, V_1, V_2, V_3, F\}$.

Figure 2. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 3. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 4. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- On the Figure (5), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 277
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- On the Figure (6), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 279
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- On the Figure (7), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 281
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- On the Figure (8), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 283
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- On the Figure (9), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 285
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- On the Figure (10), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 287
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- On the Figure (11), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 289
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- On the Figure (12), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 291
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- On the Figure (13), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 293
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- On the Figure (14), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 295
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- On the Figure (15), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 297
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- On the Figure (16), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 299
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- On the Figure (17), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 301
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Figure 5. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs mentioned as the SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 6. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 7. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs depicted SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 8. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with dense SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 9. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a messy SuperHyper-Modeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 10. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with highly-embedding-connected SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 11. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 12. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with highly-multiple-connected-style SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 13. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 14. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 17. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a Linearly-over-packed SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- On the Figure (18), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 303
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- On the Figure (19), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 305
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- On the Figure (20), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 307
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- On the Figure (21), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 309
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- On the Figure (22), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 311
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Definition 3.7 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3). 313
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Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items. 315
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- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**; 319
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**; 320
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**; 321
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**; 322
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- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**; 324
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Figure 18. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 19. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 22. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

(vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**. 326
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If we choose different types of binary operations, then we could get hugely diverse types of general forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG). 328
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Definition 3.8 (t-norm). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3). 330

A binary operation $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a **t-norm** if it satisfies the following for $x, y, z, w \in [0, 1]$: 331
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- (i) $1 \otimes x = x$; 333
- (ii) $x \otimes y = y \otimes x$; 334
- (iii) $x \otimes (y \otimes z) = (x \otimes y) \otimes z$; 335
- (iv) If $w \leq x$ and $y \leq z$ then $w \otimes y \leq x \otimes z$. 336

Definition 3.9. The **degree of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$ (with respect to t-norm T_{norm}):

$$T_A(X) = T_{norm}[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = T_{norm}[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$F_A(X) = T_{norm}[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.10. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$supp(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.11. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). 337

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where 338
339

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ; 340
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 341 342
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ; 343 344
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'})) : T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$); 345 346
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 347
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$); 348
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$); 349
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$). 350

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'})$, $I'_V(E_{i'})$, and $F'_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets. 351 352 353 354 355 356 357 358 359 360

Definition 3.12 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3). 361 362

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items. 363 364 365 366

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**; 367
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**; 368
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**; 369
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**; 370 371
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**; 372 373
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**. 374 375

This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities. 376 377 378

Definition 3.13. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same. 379 380

Figure 23. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions in the Example (3.15)

To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable.

Definition 3.14. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows.

- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions;
- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges;
- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges;
- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex.

Example 3.15. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the notion.

Example 3.16. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is up.

Figure 25. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.17)

Figure 26. Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Example (3.18)

Figure 27. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions in the Example (3.19)

Figure 28. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.20)

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold:

- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$.

Definition 3.22. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**;
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}, |E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's $V_i, |V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**;
- (iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**;
- (iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| \geq 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath**.

Definition 3.23 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). (Ref. [1], Definition 5.3, p.7).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have

- (i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$;
- (iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$;
- (iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$.

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.27)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Definition 3.24 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [1], Definition 5.4, p.7). 455

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider 457
a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 458

- (ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic 459
t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex 460
(NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 461
- (x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic 462
i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex 463
(NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 464
- (xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic 465
f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex 466
(NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 467
- (xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of 468
Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic 469
SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j 470
where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$. 471

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic notion, there's a need to “**redefine**” the 472
notion of “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. The SuperHyperVertices and the 473
SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this 474
procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. 475

Definition 3.25. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair 476
 $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds. 477

It's useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's 478
more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more 479
understandable. 480

Definition 3.26. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair 481
 $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2) 482
holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, notion, SuperHyperStar, 483
SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are 484
Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle, 485
Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite, 486
Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite, and Neutrosophic 487
SuperHyperWheel if the Table (2) holds. 488

It's useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of a Neutrosophic notion. Since there's 489
more ways to get type-results to make a Neutrosophic notion more Neutrosophicly 490
understandable. 491

Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.26)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.27)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic notion, there's a need to “**redefine**” the Neutrosophic notion of “Neutrosophic notion”. The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.27. Assume a notion. It's redefined a **Neutrosophic notion** if the Table (3) holds.

Example 3.28. Referred to the Example (3.6), assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (4).
- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (5).
- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (6).
- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (7).

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_2	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)
V_3	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 5. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.03, 0.03, 0.03)	E_2	(0, 0, 0)
V_3	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 6. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.11, 0.11, 0.11)	E_2	(0, 0, 0)
V_3	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
-	-	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 7. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0.08, 0.08, 0.08)
V_2	(0.11, 0.11, 0.11)	E_2	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)
V_3	(0.05, 0.05, 0.05)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.12, 0.12, 0.12)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)
$\{F\}$	(0.06, 0.06, 0.06)	E_5	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)
$\{H\}$	(0.08, 0.08, 0.08)	-	-
$\{N\}$	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	-	-
$\{O\}$	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	-	-

Figure 29. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

4 Main Resultant

Definition 4.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V_s' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then V_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V_s'} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s'} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s'} F(V_i))| \\
 &= \min_{V_s'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in V_s''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \quad V_j \in V_s'', \\
 & \quad \text{then } N_s^*(V_i) \in V_s'', \\
 & \quad \text{until } V_{NSHG} \setminus V_s'' = \emptyset, \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 4.2. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (29), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (8).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{12}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}$. Then V_s' is called Neutrosophic

Figure 30. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 31. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 32. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 33. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 34. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 35. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 36. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 37. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 38. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 39. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 40. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 41. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 42. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Table 8. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

SuperHyperBurning Number since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (0.52, 0.52, 0.52) = \\
 & = \min_{V_s' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |\{ (\sum_{V_i \in V_s''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} F(V_i)) | \\
 & V_7 \in V_s'', \\
 & \text{then } N_s^*(V_7) = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 7-8} \in V_s'' \\
 & \text{until } V_{NSHG} \setminus V_s'' = \emptyset, \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (30), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (9).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}$. Then V_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number since the following expressions, terms and statements is

Table 9. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 10. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number criteria holds.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (0.52, 0.52, 0.52) = \\
 & = \min_{V_s'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |\{ (\sum_{V_i \in V_s''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} F(V_i)) | \\
 & V_7 \in V_s'', \\
 & \text{then } N_s^*(V_7) = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2, 7-8} \in V_s'' \\
 & \text{until } V_{NSHG} \setminus V_s'' = \emptyset, \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (31), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (10).

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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$.

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Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a

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Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}$. Then V_s' is called Neutrosophic

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SuperHyperBurning Number since the following expressions, terms and statements is

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called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number criteria holds.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}} F(V_i))|
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 11. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (0.52, 0.52, 0.52) = \\
 &= \min_{V_s' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left\{ \left(\sum_{V_i \in V_s'} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s'} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s'} F(V_i) \right) \mid \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. V_7 \in V_s', \right. \right. \\
 &\text{then } N_s^*(V_7) = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2-3, 7-8} \in V_s' \\
 &\text{until } V_{NSHG} \setminus V_s' = \emptyset, \left. \right|.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (32), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (11).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}$. Then V_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}} T(V_i), \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}} I(V_i), \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}} F(V_i) \right| \\
 &= (0.52, 0.52, 0.52) = \\
 &= \min_{V_s' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left\{ \left(\sum_{V_i \in V_s'} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s'} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s'} F(V_i) \right) \mid \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. V_7 \in V_s', \right. \right. \\
 &\text{then } N_s^*(V_7) = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2-3, 5, 7-8} \in V_s' \\
 &\text{until } V_{NSHG} \setminus V_s' = \emptyset, \left. \right|.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (33), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (12).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}$. Then V_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number criteria holds.

$$\left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}} T(V_i), \right. \right.$$

Table 12. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 13. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=7-8}} F(V_i) | \\
 & = (0.52, 0.52, 0.52) = \\
 & = \min_{V_s' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in V_s''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \quad V_7 \in V_s'', \\
 & \text{then } N_s^*(V_7) = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 2-3,5-8} \in V_s'' \\
 & \text{until } V_{NSHG} \setminus_s V_s'' = \emptyset, \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (34), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (13).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,4}$. Then V_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyper Γ Burning Number since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyper Γ Burning Number criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & | (\sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,4}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,4}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,4}} F(V_i)) | \\
 & = (0.52, 0.52, 0.52) = \\
 & = \min_{V_s' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in V_s''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \quad V_1 \in V_s'',
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 14. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyper-Edges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

then $N_s^*(V_1) = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-7,9,10} \in V_s''$

but $V_{NSHG} \setminus V_s'' \neq \emptyset$,

$V_4 \in V_s''$,

then $N_s^*(V_4) = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1-7} \in V_s''$

until $V_{NSHG} \setminus V_s'' = \emptyset$, }|.

- On the Figure (35), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (14). 560

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. 562

Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a 563

Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1}$. Then V_s' is called Neutrosophic 564

SuperHyperBurning Number since the following expressions, terms and statements is 565

called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number criteria holds. 566

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (0.26, 0.26, 0.26) = \\
 & = \min_{V_s'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in V_s''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} F(V_i)) |
 \end{aligned}$$

$V_1 \in V_s''$,

then $N_s^*(V_1) = \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,4} \in V_s''$

until $V_{NSHG} \setminus V_s'' = \emptyset$, }|.

Example 4.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ 567
in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items. 568

- On the Figure (36), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (15). 569

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume 571

SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a 572

Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,7}$. Then V_s' is called Neutrosophic 573

SuperHyperBurning Number since the following expressions, terms and statements is 574

Table 15. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 16. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number criteria holds.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,7}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,7}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,7}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (1.04, 1.04, 1.04) = \\
 & = \min_{V_s'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V_s''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} F(V_i))| \\
 & \quad V_1 \in V_s'', \\
 & \text{then } N_s^*(V_1) = \{V_i\}_{i=2,11,15,19,24,7,32-34} \in V_s'' \\
 & \text{but } V_{NSHG} \setminus V_s'' \neq \emptyset, \\
 & \quad V_3 \in V_s'', \\
 & \text{then } N_s^*(V_3) = \{V_i\}_{i=8-10,12-14,31} \in V_s'' \\
 & \text{but } V_{NSHG} \setminus V_s'' \neq \emptyset, \\
 & \quad V_5 \in V_s'', \\
 & \text{then } N_s^*(V_5) = \{V_i\}_{i=6,16-18,20-23} \in V_s'' \\
 & \text{but } V_{NSHG} \setminus V_s'' \neq \emptyset, \\
 & \quad V_7 \in V_s'', \\
 & \text{then } N_s^*(V_7) = \{V_i\}_{i=25-30} \in V_s'' \\
 & \text{until } V_{NSHG} \setminus V_s'' = \emptyset|.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (37), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (16).

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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume

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Table 17. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,25}$. Then V_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,25}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,25}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,25}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (1.04, 1.04, 1.04) = \\
 & = \min_{V_s'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V_s''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} F(V_i))| \\
 & \quad V_3 \in V_s'', \\
 & \text{then } N_s^*(V_3) = \{V_i\}_{i=8-10,12-14,31} \in V_s'' \\
 & \text{but } V_{NSHG} \setminus_s V_s'' \neq \emptyset, \\
 & \quad V_5 \in V_s'', \\
 & \text{then } N_s^*(V_5) = \{V_i\}_{i=6,16-18,20-23} \in V_s'' \\
 & \text{but } V_{NSHG} \setminus_s V_s'' \neq \emptyset, \\
 & \quad V_{25} \in V_s'', \\
 & \text{then } N_s^*(V_{25}) = \{V_i\}_{i=26-30} \in V_s'' \\
 & \text{until } V_{NSHG} \setminus_s V_s'' = \emptyset|.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (38), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (17).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,25}$. Then V_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,25}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,25}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,25}} F(V_i))|
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 18. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,25}} F(V_i) | \\
 &= (1.04, 1.04, 1.04) = \\
 &= \min_{V_s'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in V_s''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \quad V_5 \in V_s'', \\
 & \text{then } N_s^*(V_5) = \{V_i\}_{i=6,16-18,20-23} \in V_s'' \\
 & \text{but } V_{NSHG} \setminus V_s'' \neq \emptyset, \\
 & \quad V_{25} \in V_s'', \\
 & \text{then } N_s^*(V_{25}) = \{V_i\}_{i=26-30} \in V_s'' \\
 & \text{until } V_{NSHG} \setminus V_s'' = \emptyset |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (39), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (18). 590
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,25}$. Then V_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number criteria holds. 592
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & | (\sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,25}} T(V_i), \\
 & \quad \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,25}} I(V_i), \\
 & \quad \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,25}} F(V_i)) | \\
 &= (1.04, 1.04, 1.04) = \\
 &= \min_{V_s'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in V_s''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \quad V_{25} \in V_s'', \\
 & \text{then } N_s^*(V_{25}) = \{V_i\}_{i=26-30} \in V_s'' \\
 & \text{until } V_{NSHG} \setminus V_s'' = \emptyset |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (40), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (19). 597
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a 599
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Table 19. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

Table 20. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,27}$. Then V_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyper^TBurning Number since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyper^TBurning Number criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,25}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,25}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,5,25}} F(V_i))| \\
 & = (1.04, 1.04, 1.04) = \\
 & = \min_{V_s'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in V_s''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} F(V_i))| \\
 & \quad V_i \in V_s'', \\
 & \text{then } N_s^*(V_i) = \{V_j\} \in V_s'' \\
 & \text{until } V_{NSHG} \setminus_s V_s'' = \emptyset|.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (41), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (20).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,17,22,27}$. Then V_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyper^TBurning Number since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyper^TBurning Number criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,17,22,27}} T(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,17,22,27}} I(V_i), \\
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,17,22,27}} F(V_i))|
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 21. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,3,17,22,27}} F(V_i) \\
 &= (1.3, 1.3, 1.3) = \\
 &= \min_{V_s'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V_s''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} F(V_i) \right) \right| \\
 & \quad V_i \in V_s'', \\
 & \text{then } N_s^*(V_i) = \{V_j\} \in V_s'' \\
 & \text{until } V_{NSHG} \setminus_s V_s'' = \emptyset|.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (42), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (21). 611
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Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,8,12,17,22,27}$. Then V_s' is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number since the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number criteria holds. 613
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,8,12,17,22,27}} T(V_i), \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,8,12,17,22,27}} I(V_i), \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \sum_{V_i \in V_s' = \{V_i\}_{i=1,8,12,17,22,27}} F(V_i) \right) \left| \right. \\
 &= (1.56, 1.56, 1.56) = \\
 &= \min_{V_s'' \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in V_s''} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in V_s''} F(V_i) \right) \right| \\
 & \quad V_i \in V_s'', \\
 & \text{then } N_s^*(V_i) = \{V_j\} \in V_s'' \\
 & \text{until } V_{NSHG} \setminus_s V_s'' = \emptyset|.
 \end{aligned}$$

5 Main Result 618

Theorem 5.1. (Main Result and Main Theorem). 619

Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite has the letter z . The notion on the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite and Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle don't coincide. 620
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Proof.

(i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperBurning Number taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.2. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM$ be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number set is as follows.*

$$\{V_1^{P_i}, V_2^{P_i}\}, V_3^{P_i}, \dots, V_{|P_i|}^{P_i}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.3. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM$ be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number number is as follows.*

$$|P_i| \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.4. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (ESHC) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number set is as follows.*

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} V_i^{INTERNAL}, \\ V_{i+1}^{INTERNAL}, \dots \\ V_{|E_i|}^{INTERNAL} \end{array} \right\}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \left\{ \begin{array}{l} V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{array} \right\}$$

$$P : \left\{ \begin{array}{l} V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{array} \right\}$$

is a longest SuperHyperBurning Number taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.5. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (ESHC) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number number is as follows.*

$$|E_i| \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \left\{ \begin{array}{l} V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{array} \right\}$$

$$P : \left\{ \begin{array}{l} V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \end{array} \right\}$$

$$V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperBurning Number taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Definition 5.6. (Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite and Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle).

- (i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Every pair of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the same maximum letter, i.e., Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices mutually has the same maximum letter. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$ is called **Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite**.
- (ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Every pair of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the same maximum letter, i.e., Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices mutually has the same maximum letter. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$ is called **Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle**.

Proposition 5.7. Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM$ be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number set is as follows.

$$\{V_1^{P_i}, V_2^{P_i}\}, V_3^{P_i}, \dots, V_{|P_i|}^{P_i}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv$$

$$\begin{aligned} \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.8. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite ESHM be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number number is as follows.*

$$|P_i| \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite ESHM : (V, E) . There’s a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.9. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (ESHC) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number set is as follows.*

$$\begin{aligned} \{ \\ V_i^{INTERNAL}, \\ V_{i+1}^{INTERNAL}, \dots \\ V_{|E_i|}^{INTERNAL} \\ \} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \end{aligned}$$

$$V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperBurning Number taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.10. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (ESH C) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number number is as follows.*

$$|E_i| \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperBurning Number taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.11. *(Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite and Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle).*

(i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, from different SuperHyperParts, have the maximum letter. Then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have the same maximum letter, are in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number set.

(ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic EXTERNAL SuperHyperVertices with distance two have the maximum letter. Then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have the same maximum letter, are in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number set.

Proof.

(i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperBurning Number taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning

Number. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.12. (*Embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar*).

- (i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, from different SuperHyperParts, is in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number set.
- (ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then every Neutrosophic EXTERNAL SuperHyperVertices with distance two is in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number set.

Proof.

(i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperBurning Number taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

6 Neutrosophic Applications in Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

The cancer is the Neutrosophic disease but the Neutrosophic model is going to figure out what's going on this Neutrosophic phenomenon. The special Neutrosophic case of this Neutrosophic disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer could help to find some Neutrosophic treatments for this Neutrosophic disease.

In the following, some Neutrosophic steps are Neutrosophic devised on this disease.

Step 1. (Neutrosophic Definition) The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer in the long-term Neutrosophic function.

Step 2. (Neutrosophic Issue) The specific region has been assigned by the Neutrosophic model [it's called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] and the long Neutrosophic cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done.

Step 3. (Neutrosophic Model) There are some specific Neutrosophic models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general Neutrosophic models. The moves and the Neutrosophic traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperBurning Number, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number in those Neutrosophic Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels.

Figure 44. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number

Table 23. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

8 Case 2: The Increasing Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (44), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. By using the Neutrosophic Figure (44) and the Table (23), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is obtained. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (44), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number.

9 Wondering Open Problems But As The Directions To Forming The Motivations

In what follows, some “problems” and some “questions” are proposed. The SuperHyperBurning Number and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number are defined on a real-world application, titled “Cancer’s Recognitions”.

Question 9.1. Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer’s

recognitions?

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Question 9.2. *Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperBurning Number and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number?*

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Question 9.3. *Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them?*

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Question 9.4. *Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperBurning Number and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number?*

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Problem 9.5. *The SuperHyperBurning Number and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBurning Number do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer's recognitions and they're based on SuperHyperBurning Number, are there else?*

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Problem 9.6. *Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results?*

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Problem 9.7. *What's the independent research based on Cancer's recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions?*

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10 Conclusion and Closing Remarks

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In this section, closing and concluding remarks are presented. The drawbacks of this scientific research are shown. Some advantages and disadvantages of this scientific research are highlighted.

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This scientific research uses some approaches to further understand the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs. In this effort, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the Burning Number. For this reason, in the second definition, the original definition of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the new Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph definition, the new SuperHyperNotion, Neutrosophic Burning Number, finds a suitable background to implement some results on. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses are the subjects of this scientific research on modeling areas that are subject to cancer attacks in order to recognize this disease as mentioned under the title "Cancer Diagnosis". To formalize the SuperHyperNotion, Burning Number, SuperHyperClasses and new SuperHyperClasses instances are introduced. Some general results are summarized in the Burning Number and Neutrosophic Burning Number sections. Clarifications, examples, and literature reviews go all the way. In this scientific research, the literature review has met the lines containing concepts and results. SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are super-hypermodels in "cancer diagnosis" and both are the foundation of the background of this scientific research. Sometimes cancer has occurred in an area full of cells, cell groups, and embedded styles. In this section, SuperHyperModel proposes SuperHyperNotions, formally called "Burning Number", based on the connections of Cancer's movements in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of design and architecture, in terms of terms and whispering words. . The "SuperHyper" prefix refers to the topic of embedded styles to explore the background of SuperHyperNotions. In the table (24), the advantages and ways of this scientific research are specified, pointed out and expressed.

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11 Background

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There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this scientific research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them.

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Table 24. A look at this scientific research and beyond

Advantages	Limitations
1. Redefining the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph	1. General Results
2. Burning Number	
3. Neutrosophic Burning Number	2. Other SuperHyperNumbers
4. modeling cancer diagnoses	
5. SuperHyperClasses	3. SuperHyperFamilies

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot*” in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms with introducing used neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Current Trends in Mass Communication (CTMC)*” with ISO abbreviation “*Curr Trends Mass Comm*” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 32-55.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*” in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Treatments. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*A Research on Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic Super Hypergraph by Eulerian Super Hyper Cycles and Hamiltonian Sets as Hyper Covering Versus Super separations*” in **Ref. [3]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Recognition. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 2 and issue 3 with pages 136-148. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction to Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Beyond*” in **Ref. [4]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 2 and issue 6 with pages 221-307. The research article studies

deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph by Initial Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Initial Eulogy on Super Initial EULA*" in **Ref. [5]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research*" with ISO abbreviation "IJPAMR" in volume 3 and issue 2 with pages 60-88 and doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.60-88. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut*" in **Ref. [6]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research*" with ISO abbreviation "IJPAMR" in volume 3 and issue 2 with pages 102-124 and doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.102-124. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes*" in **Ref. [7]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*" with ISO abbreviation "J Math Techniques Comput Math" in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages 242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic hypergraphs*" in **Ref. [8]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Journal of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)*" with ISO abbreviation "J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res" in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 16-24. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background. In some articles are titled "*0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph*" in **Ref. [9]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "*0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs*" in **Ref. [10]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer's Recognition as the Model in The Setting of*

(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [11]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [13]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*” in **Ref. [14]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [15]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [16]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [18]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*” in **Ref. [19]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*” in **Ref. [20]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [21]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [22]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*” in **Ref. [23]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*” in **Ref. [24]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*” in **Ref. [25]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*” in **Ref. [26]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*” in **Ref. [27]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*” in **Ref. [28]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [261]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “*The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [262]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [263]** by Henry Garrett (2023),

“Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [264]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *“Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”* in **Ref. [267]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *“Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique”* in **Ref. [268]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *“Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”* in **Ref. [271]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *“Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”* in **Ref. [274]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *“Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints”* in **Ref. [275]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *“(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”* in **Ref. [276]** by Henry Garrett (2023), *“Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond”* in **Ref. [277]** by Henry Garrett (2022), *“(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”* in **Ref. [278]** by Henry Garrett (2022), *“Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”* in **Ref. [279]** by Henry Garrett (2022), *“Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph”* in **Ref. [290]** by Henry Garrett (2022), *“Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)”* in **Ref. [291]** by Henry Garrett (2022), and [4–291], there are some endeavors to formalize the basic SuperHyperNotions about neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph alongside scientific research books at [292–439]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd in the terms of high readers, 5679 and 6667 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [440, 441].

Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [440]** by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 5679 readers in Scribd. It’s titled *“Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs”* and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book covers different types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory.

Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [441]** by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 6667 readers in Scribd. It’s titled *“Neutrosophic Duality”* and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book presents different types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set, simultaneously. It’s smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what’s done in this research book which is popular in the terms of high readers in Scribd.

See the seminal scientific researches [1–3]. The formalization of the notions on the framework of notions in SuperHyperGraphs, Neutrosophic notions in SuperHyperGraphs theory, and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs theory at [4–291] alongside scientific research books at [292–439]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd ,in the terms of high readers, 5679 and 6667 respectively, on neutrosophic

science is on [440, 441].

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References

1097

1. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot”, *Curr Trends Mass Comm* 2(1) (2023) 32-55. (doi: 10.33140/CTMC.02.01.03). 1098
1099
1100
2. Henry Garrett, “Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments”, *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(1) (2023) 35-47. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.01.05). 1101
1102
1103
1104
3. Henry Garrett, “A Research on Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic Super Hypergraph by Eulerian Super Hyper Cycles and Hamiltonian Sets as Hyper Covering Versus Super separations”, *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(3) (2023) 136-148. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.03.03). 1105
1106
1107
1108
4. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction to Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Beyond”, *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(6) (2023) 221-307. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.06.04). 1109
1110
1111
1112
5. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph by Initial Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Initial Eulogy on Super Initial EULA”, *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research* 3(2) (2023) 60-88. (doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.60-88). 1113
1114
1115
1116
6. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut”, *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research* 3(2) (2023) 102-124. (doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.102-124). 1117
1118
1119
1120
7. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut”, *J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res* 2(1) (2023) 16-24. (doi: 10.33140/JCTCSR.02.01.04) 1121
1122
1123
1124
8. Henry Garrett, “Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes”, *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 1(3) (2022) 242-263. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.01.03.09) 1125
1126
1127
1128
9. Garrett, Henry. “0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph.” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Nov. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6319942>. <https://oa.mg/work/10.5281/zenodo.6319942> 1129
1130
1131
1132
1133
1134
10. Garrett, Henry. “0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs.” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Feb. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724>. <https://oa.mg/work/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724> 1135
1136
1137
1138
1139

11. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 1140-1143
12. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 1144-1147
13. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1). 1148-1150
14. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 1151-1156
15. Henry Garrett, “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 1157-1160
16. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 1161-1164
17. Henry Garrett, “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 1165-1168
18. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1169-1171
19. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 1172-1175
20. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044 1176-1178
21. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 1179-1181
22. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1182-1185

23. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1).
1186
1187
1188
1189
24. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1).
1190
1191
1192
25. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1).
1193
1194
1195
1196
1197
26. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1).
1198
1199
1200
27. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1).
1201
1202
1203
1204
28. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1).
1205
1206
1207
1208
29. Henry Garrett, “*Star and Wheel on Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph with a Specific Type of Independency of SuperHyperVertices*”, Preprints 2024, , 2024020663 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202402.0663.v1).
1209
1210
1211
1212
30. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Zero Forcing From Graph Searching*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12788786).
1213
1214
1215
31. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Zero Forcing*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12752339).
1216
1217
1218
32. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Zero Forcing*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12738172).
1219
1220
1221
33. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Connected Perfect Dual Domination*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12680424).
1222
1223
1224
34. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Connected Perfect Dual Domination*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12675758).
1225
1226
1227
35. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Connected Perfect Dual Domination*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12656919).
1228
1229
1230

36. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12576337). 1231
1232
1233
37. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12556338). 1234
1235
1236
38. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12536399). 1237
1238
1239
39. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12174846). 1240
1241
1242
40. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12129978). 1243
1244
1245
41. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12024191). 1246
1247
1248
42. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Connected Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11661528). 1249
1250
1251
43. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Connected Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11651866). 1252
1253
1254
44. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Connected Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11634496). 1255
1256
1257
45. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11513482). 1258
1259
1260
46. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11479559). 1261
1262
1263
47. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11438586). 1264
1265
1266
48. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11253553). 1267
1268
1269
49. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11218489). 1270
1271
1272
50. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11169069). 1273
1274
1275

51. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11075522). 1276
1277
1278
52. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10982844). 1279
1280
1281
53. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10963312). 1282
1283
1284
54. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10929590). 1285
1286
1287
55. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10918770). 1288
1289
1290
56. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10910154). 1291
1292
1293
57. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10899659). 1294
1295
1296
58. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10895887). 1297
1298
1299
59. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10888691). 1300
1301
1302
60. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Star and Counteroffer Wheel By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10851065). 1303
1304
1305
1306
61. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Bipartite and Counteroffer Path By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10796076). 1307
1308
1309
1310
62. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Multipartite and Counteroffer Cycle By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10640905). 1311
1312
1313
1314
63. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17389.97769). 1315
1316
1317
1318

64. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28685.10727). 1319
1320
1321
1322
65. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.24994.20169). 1323
1324
1325
1326
66. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10371529). 1327
1328
1329
67. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10299535). 1330
1331
1332
68. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10263440). 1333
1334
1335
1336
69. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10028600). 1337
1338
1339
70. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8310454). 1340
1341
1342
71. Henry Garrett, “Recognition of Cancer With Bipartite and Path as Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By the Tool Called Stability”, Preprints 2023, 2023081972 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202308.1972.v1). 1343
1344
1345
72. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8262182). 1346
1347
1348
73. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206877). 1349
1350
1351
1352
74. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206834). 1353
1354
1355
1356
75. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206773). 1357
1358
1359
1360
76. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201319). 1361
1362
1363
1364

77. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201255). 1365
1366
1367
1368
78. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201165). 1369
1370
1371
1372
79. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196147). 1373
1374
1375
1376
80. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196132). 1377
1378
1379
1380
81. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196099). 1381
1382
1383
1384
82. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8187955). 1385
1386
1387
83. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8161878). 1388
1389
1390
84. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8176262). 1391
1392
1393
85. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect Search As Hyper Perf On Super Perfidy”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104836). 1394
1395
1396
86. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Perfidy By Hyper Perf Of SuperHyperPerfect Search In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104857). 1397
1398
1399
87. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092796). 1400
1401
1402
88. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092766). 1403
1404
1405
89. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Unequal Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8088438). 1406
1407
1408

90. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Unequal Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8088387). 1409
1410
1411
91. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Strict Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8084436). 1412
1413
1414
92. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Strict Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8084420). 1415
1416
1417
93. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Strict Connective As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080100). 1418
1419
1420
94. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Reverse Strict Connective In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080068). 1421
1422
1423
95. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Unequal Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078445). 1424
1425
1426
96. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Unequal Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078543). 1427
1428
1429
97. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Strict Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076416). 1430
1431
1432
98. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Strict Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076399). 1433
1434
1435
99. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072171). 1436
1437
1438
100. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Reverse Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072267). 1439
1440
1441
101. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Equal Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067384). 1442
1443
1444
102. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Equal Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067409). 1445
1446
1447
103. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8061927). 1448
1449
1450
104. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8062016). 1451
1452
1453

105. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057696). 1454
1455
1456
106. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Reverse Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057753). 1457
1458
1459
107. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Equal Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052893). 1460
1461
1462
108. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Equal Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052925). 1463
1464
1465
109. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051346). 1466
1467
1468
110. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051360). 1469
1470
1471
111. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By United Dominating As Hyper Ultra On Super Units”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8025707). 1472
1473
1474
112. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Units By Hyper Ultra Of United Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8027275). 1475
1476
1477
113. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Zero Forcing As Hyper ford On Super forceps”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8017246). 1478
1479
1480
114. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super forceps By Hyper ford Of Zero Forcing In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8020128). 1481
1482
1483
115. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Matrix-Based As Hyper mat On Super matte”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978571). 1484
1485
1486
116. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super mat By Hyper matte Of Matrix-Based In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978857). 1487
1488
1489
117. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Dominating-Edges As Hyper Dome On Super Eddy”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7940830). 1490
1491
1492
118. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Eddy By Hyper Dome Of Dominating-Edges In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943578). 1493
1494
1495
119. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Gap As Hyper Gape On Super Gab”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7916595). 1496
1497
1498

120. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Gab By Hyper Gape Of Edge-Gap In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7923632). 1499
1500
1501
121. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904698). 1502
1503
1504
122. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904671). 1505
1506
1507
123. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904529). 1508
1509
1510
1511
124. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904401). 1512
1513
1514
1515
125. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7871026). 1516
1517
1518
126. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7874647). 1519
1520
1521
127. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857856). 1522
1523
1524
128. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857841). 1525
1526
1527
129. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7855661). 1528
1529
1530
130. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7855637). 1531
1532
1533
131. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7853867). 1534
1535
1536
132. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7853922). 1537
1538
1539
133. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851519). 1540
1541
1542

134. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph)*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851550). 1543
1544
1545
135. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7839333). 1546
1547
1548
136. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph)*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7840206). 1549
1550
1551
137. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7834229). 1552
1553
1554
138. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph)*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7834261). 1555
1556
1557
139. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7824560). 1558
1559
1560
140. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Path-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph)*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7824623). 1561
1562
1563
141. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7819531). 1564
1565
1566
142. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Path-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph)*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7819579). 1567
1568
1569
143. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812236). 1570
1571
1572
144. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By initial Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper initial Eulogy On Super initial EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809365). 1573
1574
1575
145. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut On Super EULA-Path-Cut*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809358). 1576
1577
1578
146. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Path-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph)*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809219). 1579
1580
1581
147. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809328). 1582
1583
1584
148. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7806767). 1585
1586
1587

149. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7806838). 1588
1589
1590
150. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804238). 1591
1592
1593
1594
151. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804228). 1595
1596
1597
152. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7799902). 1598
1599
1600
153. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804218). 1601
1602
1603
154. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7796334). 1604
1605
1606
155. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7793372). 1607
1608
1609
156. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7791952). 1610
1611
1612
157. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7791982). 1613
1614
1615
158. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790026). 1616
1617
1618
159. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Hamiltonian-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790052). 1619
1620
1621
160. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787066). 1622
1623
1624
161. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Hamiltonian-Decomposition In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787094). 1625
1626
1627
162. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7781476). 1628
1629
1630

163. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7783082). 1631
1632
1633
164. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7777857). 1634
1635
1636
165. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Trace-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7779286). 1637
1638
1639
166. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7771831). 1640
1641
1642
167. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Trace-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7772468). 1643
1644
1645
168. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Cut As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20913.25446). 1646
1647
1648
169. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Tract By Hyper Track Of Trace-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7764916). 1649
1650
1651
170. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11770.98247). 1652
1653
1654
171. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Edge-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12400.12808). 1655
1656
1657
172. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22545.10089). 1658
1659
1660
173. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Edge-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29544.34564). 1661
1662
1663
174. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Cut As Hyper Edify On Super Eddy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11377.76644). 1664
1665
1666
175. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Eddy By Hyper Edify Of Edge-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23750.96329). 1667
1668
1669
176. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31366.24641). 1670
1671
1672
177. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Vertex-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34721.68960). 1673
1674
1675

178. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30212.81289). 1676
1677
1678
179. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Vertex-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18468.76169). 1679
1680
1681
180. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Cut As Hyper Vertu On Super Vertigo*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.24288.35842). 1682
1683
1684
181. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Vertigo By Hyper Vertu Of Vertex-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32467.25124). 1685
1686
1687
182. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31025.45925). 1688
1689
1690
183. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulizer By Hyper Nub Of Stable-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17184.25602). 1691
1692
1693
184. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Decompositions As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23423.28327). 1694
1695
1696
185. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28456.44805). 1697
1698
1699
186. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Cut As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23525.68320). 1700
1701
1702
187. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20170.24000). 1703
1704
1705
188. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Neighbors As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36475.59683). 1706
1707
1708
189. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulizer By Hyper Nub Of Clique-Neighbors In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29764.71046). 1709
1710
1711
190. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Decompositions As Hyper Decompile On Super Decommission*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18780.87683). 1712
1713
1714
191. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Clique- Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27169.48487). 1715
1716
1717
192. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Cut As Hyper Click On Super Cliche*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26134.01603). 1718
1719
1720

193. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Cliff By Hyper Cling Of Clique-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27392.30721). 1721
1722
1723
194. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Spin On Super Spacy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33028.40321). 1724
1725
1726
195. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By List- Coloring As Hyper List On Super Lisle*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21389.20966). 1727
1728
1729
196. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Lith By Hyper Lite Of List-Coloring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16356.04489). 1730
1731
1732
197. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Sparse On Super Spark*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21756.21129). 1733
1734
1735
198. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Solidarity By Hyper Soul Of Space In Cancer’s Recognition With (Extreme) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30983.68009). 1736
1737
1738
199. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Connectivity As Hyper Disclosure On Super Closure*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28552.29445). 1739
1740
1741
200. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Uniform By Hyper Deformation Of Edge-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10936.21761). 1742
1743
1744
201. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Connectivity As Hyper Leak On Super Structure*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35105.89447). 1745
1746
1747
202. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super System By Hyper Explosions Of Vertex-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30072.72960). 1748
1749
1750
203. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Tree-Decomposition As Hyper Forward On Super Returns*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31147.52003). 1751
1752
1753
204. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nodes By Hyper Moves Of Tree-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32825.24163). 1754
1755
1756
205. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Chord As Hyper Excellence On Super Excess*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13059.58401). 1757
1758
1759
206. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Gap By Hyper Navigations Of Chord In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11172.14720). 1760
1761
1762
207. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination As Hyper Controller On Super Waves*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22011.80165). 1763
1764
1765

208. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Coincidence By Hyper Routes Of SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30819.84003). 1766
1767
1768
209. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperEdge-Domination As Hyper Reversion On Super Indirection*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10493.84962). 1769
1770
1771
210. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Obstacles By Hyper Model Of SuperHyperEdge-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13849.29280). 1772
1773
1774
211. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Domination As Hyper k-Actions On Super Patterns*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19944.14086). 1775
1776
1777
212. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Harmony By Hyper k-Function Of SuperHyperK-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23299.58404). 1778
1779
1780
213. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Number As Hyper k-Partition On Super Layers*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33103.76968). 1781
1782
1783
214. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Gradient By Hyper k-Class Of SuperHyperK-Number In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23037.44003). 1784
1785
1786
215. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperOrder As Hyper Enumerations On Super Landmarks*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35646.56641). 1787
1788
1789
216. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Analogous By Hyper Visions Of SuperHyperOrder In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18030.48967). 1790
1791
1792
217. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Categories On Super Neighbors*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13973.81121). 1793
1794
1795
218. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Relations By Hyper Identifications Of SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34106.47047). 1796
1797
1798
219. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Contradiction By Hyper Detection of SuperHyperDefensive In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13397.09446). 1799
1800
1801
220. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDimension As Hyper Distinguishing On Super Distances*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31956.88961). 1802
1803
1804
221. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Locations By Hyper Differing Of SuperHyperDimension In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15179.67361). 1805
1806
1807
222. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDominating As Hyper Closing On Super Messy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21510.45125). 1808
1809
1810

223. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Missing By Hyper Searching Of SuperHyperDominating In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13121.84321). 1811
1812
1813
224. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnected As Hyper Group On Super Surge*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11758.69441). 1814
1815
1816
225. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Outbreak By Hyper Collections Of SuperHyperConnected In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31891.35367). 1817
1818
1819
226. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperTotal As Hyper Covering On Super Infections*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19360.87048). 1820
1821
1822
227. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Extremism By Hyper Treatments Of SuperHyperTotal In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32363.21286). 1823
1824
1825
228. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Isolation By Hyper Perfectness Of SuperHyperPerfect In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23266.81602). 1826
1827
1828
229. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect As Hyper Idealism On Super Vacancy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19911.37285). 1829
1830
1831
230. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperJoin As Hyper Separations On Super Sorts*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11050.90569). 1832
1833
1834
231. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super connections By Hyper disconnections Of SuperHyperJoin In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17761.79206). 1835
1836
1837
232. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Mixed-Devastations By Hyper Decisions Of SuperHyperDuality In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34953.52320). 1838
1839
1840
233. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDuality As Hyper Imaginations On Super Mixed-Illustrations*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33275.80161). 1841
1842
1843
234. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By Path SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Correction On Super Faults*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30182.50241). 1844
1845
1846
235. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Reflections By Hyper Rotations Of Path SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33459.30243). 1847
1848
1849
236. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas As Hyper Deformations On Super Chains In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDensity*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13444.60806). 1850
1851
1852
237. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas As Hyper Ignorance By SuperHyperDensity On Super Resistances In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.16800.05123). 1853
1854
1855

238. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-VI*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29913.80482). 1856
1857
1858
1859
239. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-V*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33269.24809). 1860
1861
1862
1863
240. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-IV*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34946.96960). 1864
1865
1866
1867
241. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-III*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14814.31040). 1868
1869
1870
1871
242. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-II*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15653.17125). 1872
1873
1874
1875
243. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-I*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25719.50089). 1876
1877
1878
1879
244. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Disruptions In Cancer’s Extreme Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hyper Plans Called SuperHyperConnectivities*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29441.94562). 1880
1881
1882
1883
245. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnectivities As Hyper Diagnosis On Super Mechanism*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17252.24968). 1884
1885
1886
246. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By the Criteria of Eulerian and Hamiltonian Type-Sets As Hyper Modified Cycles On Super Mess*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16652.59525). 1887
1888
1889
247. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian and Hamiltonian In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph On Super Interactions By Hyper Extensions of Cycles*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34583.24485). 1890
1891
1892
248. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth Type-Results on extreme SuperHyperGirth theory and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs Toward Cancer’s extreme Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010396 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0396.v1). 1893
1894
1895
1896
249. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Warns Hyper Landmark of neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth In Super Type-Versions of Cancer’s neutrosophic Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010395 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0395.v1). 1897
1898
1899
1900

250. Henry Garrett, “*The Constructions of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs on the Cancer’s Recognition in The Confrontation With Super Attacks In Hyper Situations By Implementing (Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in The Technical Approaches to Neutralize SuperHyperViews*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26240.51204). 1901-1905
251. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing As the Entrepreneurs on Cancer’s Recognitions To Fail Forcing Style As the Super Classes With Hyper Effects In The Background of the Framework is So-Called (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12818.73925). 1906-1910
252. Henry Garrett, “*Super Actions On The Types of Hyper Levels In The Sensible Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth On Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26836.88960). 1911-1914
253. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth Approaches on the Super Challenges on the Cancer’s Recognition In the Hyper Model of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36745.93289). 1915-1917
254. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 1918-1921
255. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 1922-1925
256. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1).). 1926-1928
257. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 1929-1934
258. Henry Garrett, “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 1935-1938
259. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 1939-1942
260. Henry Garrett, “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 1943-1946

261. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35061.65767). 1947
1948
1949
262. Henry Garrett, “*The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18494.15680). 1950
1951
1952
1953
263. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 1954
1955
1956
1957
264. Henry Garrett, “*Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15897.70243). 1958
1959
1960
1961
265. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 1962
1963
1964
1965
266. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1966
1967
1968
267. Henry Garrett, “*Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30092.80004). 1969
1970
1971
268. Henry Garrett, “*Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23172.19849). 1972
1973
1974
1975
269. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1976
1977
1978
1979
270. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 1980
1981
1982
1983
271. Henry Garrett, “*Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17385.36968). 1984
1985
1986
1987
272. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044 1988
1989
1990

273. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 1991
1992
1993
274. Henry Garrett, “Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28945.92007). 1994
1995
1996
275. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11447.80803). 1997
1998
1999
276. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35774.77123). 2000
2001
2002
277. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36141.77287). 2003
2004
2005
2006
278. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29430.88642). 2007
2008
2009
279. Henry Garrett, “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11369.16487). 2010
2011
2012
2013
280. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 2014
2015
2016
281. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19380.94084). 2017
2018
2019
282. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 2020
2021
2022
2023
2024
283. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14426.41923). 2025
2026
2027
2028
2029
284. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 2030
2031
2032
285. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20993.12640). 2033
2034
2035

286. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 2036
2037
2038
2039
287. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23123.04641). 2040
2041
2042
2043
288. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 2044
2045
2046
2047
289. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23324.56966). 2048
2049
2050
2051
290. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29173.86244). 2052
2053
2054
291. Henry Garrett, “*Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25385.88160). 2055
2056
2057
2058
292. Henry Garrett, “Zero Forcing In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12691570). 2059
2060
293. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 6”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12651785). 2061
2062
294. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 5”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12214087). 2063
2064
295. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 4”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11876996). 2065
2066
296. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 3”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11529821). 2067
2068
297. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 2”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11398118). 2069
2070
298. Henry Garrett, “Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 1”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11106891). 2071
2072
299. Henry Garrett, “Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 3”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10946745). 2073
2074
300. Henry Garrett, “Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 2”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10909931). 2075
2076
301. Henry Garrett, “Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10871136). 2077
2078

302. Henry Garrett, “Stable Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10523307). 2079
2080
303. Henry Garrett, “Resolving Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10395711). 2081
2082
304. Henry Garrett, “Dominating Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10042973). 2083
2084
305. Henry Garrett, “Stable In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8210033). 2085
2086
306. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206898). 2087
2088
307. Henry Garrett, “Equal Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201378). 2089
2090
308. Henry Garrett, “Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8194003). 2091
2092
309. Henry Garrett, “Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8113416). 2093
2094
310. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperPerfect Search In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104880). 2095
2096
311. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092816). 2097
2098
312. Henry Garrett, “Unequal Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8090194). 2099
2100
313. Henry Garrett, “Strict Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8086310). 2101
2102
314. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Strict Connective In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080167). 2103
2104
315. Henry Garrett, “Unequal Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078574). 2105
2106
316. Henry Garrett, “Strict Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076449). 2107
2108
317. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072310). 2109
2110
318. Henry Garrett, “Equal Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067469). 2111
2112
319. Henry Garrett, “Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8062076). 2113
2114
320. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057817). 2115
2116
321. Henry Garrett, “Equal Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052976). 2117
2118

322. Henry Garrett, “Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051368). 2119
2120
323. Henry Garrett, “United Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8027488). 2121
2122
324. Henry Garrett, “Zero Forcing In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8020181). 2123
2124
325. Henry Garrett, “Matrix-Based In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978921). 2125
2126
326. Henry Garrett, “Collections of Math II”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943878). 2127
2128
327. Henry Garrett, “Dominating-Edges In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943871). 2129
2130
328. Henry Garrett, “Edge-Gap In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7923786). 2131
2132
329. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7905287). 2133
2134
330. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904586). 2135
2136
331. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7874677). 2137
2138
332. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857906). 2139
2140
333. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7856329). 2141
2142
334. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7854561). 2143
2144
335. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851893). 2145
2146
336. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7848019). 2147
2148
337. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7835063). 2149
2150
338. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7826705). 2151
2152
339. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7820680). 2153
2154
340. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812750). 2155
2156
341. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812142). 2157
2158

342. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7810394). 2159
2160
343. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7807782). 2161
2162
344. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804449). 2163
2164
345. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7793875). 2165
2166
346. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7792307). 2167
2168
347. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790728). 2169
2170
348. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787712). 2171
2172
349. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7783791). 2173
2174
350. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7780123). 2175
2176
351. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7773119). 2177
2178
352. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDuality*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7637762). 2179
2180
353. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7766174). 2181
2182
354. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7762232). 2183
2184
355. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7758601). 2185
2186
356. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7754661). 2187
2188
357. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7750995). 2189
2190
358. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7749875). 2191
2192
359. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7747236). 2193
2194
360. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7742587). 2195
2196
361. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Decompositions In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7738635). 2197
2198

362. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7734719). 2199
2200
363. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Neighbors In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7730484). 2201
2202
364. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Decompositions In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7730469). 2203
2204
365. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7722865). 2205
2206
366. Henry Garrett, “*Space In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7713563). 2207
2208
367. Henry Garrett, “*Space In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7709116). 2209
2210
368. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Connectivity In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7706415). 2211
2212
369. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Connectivity In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7706063). 2213
2214
370. Henry Garrett, “*Tree-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7701906). 2215
2216
371. Henry Garrett, “*Chord In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7700205). 2217
2218
372. Henry Garrett, “*(i,j)-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7694876). 2219
2220
373. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7679410). 2221
2222
374. Henry Garrett, “*K-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7675982). 2223
2224
375. Henry Garrett, “*K-Number In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7672388). 2225
2226
376. Henry Garrett, “*Order In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7668648). 2227
2228
377. Henry Garrett, “*Coloring In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7662810). 2229
2230
378. Henry Garrett, “*Dimension In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7659162). 2231
2232
379. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653233). 2233
2234
380. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperWheel*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653204). 2235
2236
381. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMultipartite*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653142). 2237
2238

382. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperBipartite*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653117). 2239
2240
383. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperStar*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653089). 2241
2242
384. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651687). 2243
2244
385. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperPath*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651619). 2245
2246
386. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDomination*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651439). 2247
2248
387. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7650729). 2249
2250
388. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperConnected*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7647868). 2251
2252
389. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperTotal*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7647017). 2253
2254
390. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperPerfect*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7644894). 2255
2256
391. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperJoin*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7641880). 2257
2258
392. Henry Garrett, “*Path SuperHyperColoring*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7632923). 2259
2260
393. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDensity*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7623459). 2261
2262
394. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606416). 2263
2264
395. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606416). 2265
2266
396. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606404). 2267
2268
397. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2269
2270
398. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2271
2272
399. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2273
2274
400. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7579929). 2275
2276
401. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563170). 2277
2278

402. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563164). 2279
2280
403. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2281
2282
404. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2283
2284
405. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2285
2286
406. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7557063). 2287
2288
407. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7557009). 2289
2290
408. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7539484). 2291
2292
409. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2293
2294
410. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2295
2296
411. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2297
2298
412. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7574952). 2299
2300
413. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7574992). 2301
2302
414. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2303
2304
415. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2305
2306
416. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2307
2308
417. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2309
2310
418. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2311
2312
419. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2313
2314
420. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2315
2316
421. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2317
2318

422. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2319
2320
423. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2321
2322
424. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2323
2324
425. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2325
2326
426. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2327
2328
427. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2329
2330
428. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2331
2332
429. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2333
2334
430. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7539484). 2335
2336
431. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2337
2338
432. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2339
2340
433. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2341
2342
434. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2343
2344
435. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2345
2346
436. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2347
2348
437. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2349
2350
438. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7480110). 2351
2352
439. Henry Garrett, “*Neut. SuperHyperEdges*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7378758). 2353
2354
440. Henry Garrett, “*Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6320305). 2355
2356
441. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Duality*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6677173). 2357
2358